

A Transferable Framework for Mapping Natural Hazard Occurrence and Impacts from News Media Sources

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Summary

Natural hazards such as earthquakes, floods, and wildfires affect communities worldwide making it essential their impacts, spatial distribution and frequency are understood. News media is a widely available but underutilised source of hazard information, often containing detailed information on natural hazards and their impacts. This methodology provides a structured approach for transforming news reports into natural hazard inventories. By applying text mining, automated filtering, and GIS mapping, the method converts unstructured news reports into spatially referenced hazard records. That capture both hazard occurrence and associated impacts on infrastructure and services providing a transferable workflow applicable across regions and hazard types.

KEYWORDS: Hazard Mapping; Natural Hazard; Geographical Information Systems; News Media

1. Introduction

Natural hazards such as earthquakes, floods, and wildfires are widespread events affecting communities globally. In 2020 alone, natural hazards impacted approximately 100 million people, causing 15,082 deaths and an estimated \$190 billion in economic losses (Jones et al., 2022). Hazard databases play a central role in risk assessment by recording event characteristics, including location, magnitude, and associated impacts. When combined with GIS techniques, these inventories enable the identification of vulnerable areas, supporting policy development and guiding research (Klose et al., 2015; Gómez et al., 2023). However, the coverage and consistency of existing datasets remain highly variable, influenced by hazard type, event timing, and regional economic context (Jones et al., 2022). Furthermore, most traditional inventories focus on single hazards, limiting their ability to represent interacting processes. This is particularly significant given that 59% of global economic losses from natural hazards are attributed to multi-hazard events (Lee et al., 2024).

To address these limitations, this study presents a methodology for mapping hazard events and impacts using open-access news media. News reports represent a widely available yet underutilised source of hazard information, often containing multiple layers of extractable information within a single headline, including hazard type, location, impacts, and severity indicators. **Figure 1** illustrates how key elements such as hazard occurrence (“flooding”), location (“Caledonian Road”, “Islington”), and infrastructure impacts (“without power”) are present in the text, highlighting the potential of news media as a potential data source for hazard and impact extraction.

However, the unstructured format, linguistic diversity, and variability in reporting presents challenges for systematic analysis and mapping. To overcome this, the framework integrates text mining with GIS-based geolocation to extract, classify, and spatially reference hazard information within a transferable workflow. Enabling the generation of datasets that capture both hazard occurrence and realised impacts on systems and services.

Figure 1, Example of key information embedded within a news headline, illustrating extractable components including hazard type (**Flooding**), location (**Caledonian Road, Islington**), and infrastructure impacts (**Power Outage**). Highlighted terms demonstrate how unstructured news media can be used to derive hazard and impact data.

News Source: (Place et al., 2026)

The framework offers several advantages for hazard risk research: (i) it captures operational and functional impacts that are often excluded from conventional hazard inventories, thereby enhancing understanding of real-world consequences; (ii) it enables rapid compilation of historical datasets, supporting analysis of spatial and temporal patterns in hazard occurrence and infrastructure sensitivity; and (iii) its reliance on open-access data and open-source tools enhances reproducibility, and accessibility for researchers and practitioners.

2. Methodology

This methodology comprises of a six-stage process (**Figure 2**). An initial set of multilingual search terms is developed across four key themes: hazards, features, impacts, and locations. Place names and associated spatial coordinates are then compiled from OpenStreetMap to support geolocation. These terms are systematically combined to query news sources, enabling the extraction of relevant articles for analysis. Once this is generated LLMs can be applied to filter and sort relevant and irrelevant results providing one comprehensive database. The database can then be geocoded producing a comprehensive hazard inventory map of a region

Figure 2, Flowchart of the methodology for constructing a multilingual, news-derived multi-hazard impact database for transport infrastructure, integrating automated retrieval, LLM-assisted screening, geocoding, and mapping.

Search dictionaries are generated around four key themes: Hazard, Impact, Feature and Location (**Table 1**). These dictionaries are tailored to the specific case study to ensure relevance and adaptability across different hazard and infrastructure contexts. Hazard terms encompass Geological, Hydrological, Meteorological, and Climatological processes enabling the identification of a broad range of hazard events. Impact descriptors capture both physical damage and disruptions, such as closures, service suspension, access loss, and operational delays and can be defined flexibly. Feature terms are used to identify specific assets or systems of interest. For example, where critical infrastructure is the focus, terms may include hospitals, roads, railways, power stations, or water treatment facilities. Location names and associated latitudes and longitudes are derived from OpenStreetMap place names.

Table 1, Representative search terms used within the structured dictionary for hazard, impact, and infrastructure feature identification.

Hazard Terms	Impact Terms	Feature Terms
<p><u>Geological</u> Earthquake, Tremor, Landslide, Slope Failure, Rockfall, Debris Flow, Mudslide, Tsunami</p>	<p><u>Human Impacts</u> Fatalities, Injured, Wounded, Missing, Evacuated, Displaced, Rescued</p>	<p><u>Transport Infrastructure</u> Road, Highway, Rail, Railway, Bridge, Tunnel</p>
<p><u>Hydrological</u> Flood, Flooding, Inundation, Overflow, Flash Flood, Storm Surge, Water Level Rise</p>	<p><u>Infrastructure Impacts</u> Damage, Destroyed, Collapsed, Power Outage, Blackout, Water Supply Disruption</p>	<p><u>Energy Infrastructure</u> Power Station, Substation, Electricity, Grid, Power Line</p>
<p><u>Meteorological</u> Storm, Typhoon, Cyclone, Heavy Rain, torrential rain, thunderstorm, tornado</p>	<p><u>Economic Impacts</u> Losses, Economic Damage, Cost, Business Interruption</p>	<p><u>Water Infrastructure</u> Water Supply, Reservoir, Drainage, Sewer, Wastewater</p>
<p><u>Climatological</u> Drought, Heatwave, Extreme Heat, Wildfire, Forest Fire, Dry Conditions</p>	<p><u>Environmental Impacts</u> Contamination, Pollution, Erosion, Habitat Loss, Deforestation, Water Quality</p>	<p><u>Health Infrastructure</u> Hospital, Emergency Services, Ambulance, Public Service</p>
	<p><u>Social Impacts</u> Disruption, School Closure, Emergency Response, Humanitarian Aid, Access Restricted, Community Impact</p>	<p><u>Commercial Infrastructure</u> Factory, Warehouse, Logistics Hub, Distribution Centre</p>

Using the defined search terms, combinations are generated across hazard, impact, feature, and location categories, with searches conducted retrospectively from the date of query. A key inclusion criterion is the presence of at least one identifiable location within the article, ensuring all retained records can be geolocated. Data collection is performed using Google News and the GNews python package, selected for its role as a global news aggregator that compiles content from local, national, and international sources (Abdullah., 2024). This enables the capture of diverse reports across multiple regions and languages, supporting the scalability and transferability of the methodology.

These searches can return thousands of results, making manual verification impractical. A large language model (LLM) is therefore used to screen articles and classify their relevance to natural hazard events and associated impacts. Articles lacking hazard or transport relevance are excluded. To improve reliability, iterative manual review can be applied, with misclassified records corrected and used as feedback to refine the model, ensuring a consistent and accurate filtered dataset.

The validated dataset is geocoded by linking extracted place names to spatial features derived from OpenStreetMap, producing a spatially referenced hazard inventory. Place names are matched to a predefined geospatial dictionary. Articles without identifiable locations are excluded, while validated records are assigned coordinates and projected onto a basemap. This enables the integration of hazard occurrence and associated impacts within a GIS framework. Spatial analysis techniques, including point mapping, density estimation, and thematic classification, can then be applied to identify patterns in hazard distribution, infrastructure exposure, and impact types. These outputs provide empirical, observation-based evidence of hazard occurrence and its effects.

3. Results

We applied this methodologies across two cases to represent small- and large-scale searches across different languages. The results of this work show the widespread applicability of this framework across different regions and languages including English and Traditional Chinese (**Figures 3 & 4**). In the UK, a total of 493 articles were retrieved for the West Midlands region. These records were classified by hazard type, revealing a diverse range of events. The most frequently identified hazards include snow and ice (91 records), flooding (74), and storms (66), alongside additional categories such as weather warnings (27) and extreme rainfall (24). Infrastructure-related impacts were also captured, including power outages (15) and infrastructure damage (14), demonstrating the framework's ability to identify both hazard events and their associated consequences. Whilst an additional case study of Taiwan, showed the methodology was able to produce a substantially larger dataset, with 6,720 articles. These records were grouped into four primary hazard classes: meteorological (3,810 events), hydrological (1,610), geological (3,224), and fire-related (281). A total of 3,924 records were associated with a single hazard type, while approximately 5,000 records contained multiple hazard classifications, indicating the presence of compound hazard conditions and overlapping impacts.

The spatial outputs (**Figures 3 and 4**) demonstrate the successful integration of extracted information within a GIS environment, producing coherent hazard inventories that capture both spatial patterns and infrastructure exposure. Together, these results highlight the applicability of the framework across different geographic and linguistic contexts.

Figure 3, Spatial distribution of hazard events and associated infrastructure impacts derived from news media across the West Midlands. Points are colour-coded by hazard type, illustrating the ability of the framework to capture diverse hazard processes and their impacts within a spatially explicit dataset.

Figure 4, Spatial Distribution of returned hazard results within Taiwan broken down by hazard type, Panel (a.) maps all Geological Hazards including landslides, rockfalls, and slope failures, Panel (b.) represents Hydrometeorological Hazards such as flooding, heavy rainfall, and debris flows

4. Conclusions

This study demonstrates the scalable potential of open-access news media to generate hazard inventories and impact databases across diverse geographic and hazard contexts. The approach captures multi-hazard events across regions, enabling consistent geocoding and classification of impacts through systematic text mining and bespoke multilingual search-term databases. Given the large volume of retrieved records, large language model (LLM) filtering is implemented as an assistant auditor, enabling rapid and consistent screening while improving dataset accuracy and reducing manual effort.

The extracted information is transformed into a spatial dataset by linking place names found in the news articles to geolocated features from OpenStreetMap, enabling the construction of a hazard database that can be mapped and analysed. Application in the West Midlands and Taiwan demonstrates the ability to identify spatial patterns of hazard risk and infrastructure impacts across different sites and languages.

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